

Algorithmic Mirror: Designing an Interactive Tool to Promote Self-Reflection for YouTube Recommendations

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Fig. 1. Four-step workflow for reflective exploration of YouTube recommendations in Algorithmic Mirror: (A) Export watch history via Google Takeout, (B) Process via semantic analysis using Latent Lab, (C) Generate a semantic map of video topics and sources (pulled vs. pushed content), and (D) Reflect on interests and algorithmic recommendations—illustrated by interconnected nodes.

Big Data analytics and Artificial Intelligence systems derive non-intuitive and often unverifiable inferences about individuals' behaviors, preferences, and private lives. Drawing on diverse, feature-rich datasets of unpredictable value, these systems erode the intuitive connection between our actions and how we are perceived, diminishing control over our digital identities. While Explainable Artificial Intelligence scholars have attempted to explain the inner workings of algorithms, their visualizations frequently overwhelm end-users with complexity. This research introduces 'hypothetical inference'—a novel approach that uses language models to simulate how algorithms might interpret users' digital footprints and infer personal characteristics without requiring access to proprietary platform algorithms. Through empirical studies with fourteen participants, we advance the discourse on algorithmic literacy by providing users with accessible insights into potential algorithmic interpretations of their data.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Online, recognizing and identifying one's own image is a difficult but important task. Recognizing oneself helps develop self-consciousness and introspection, a process that Lacan calls 'mirror stage' [10]. The mirror allows individuals to encounter their reflection and construct an image of a unified self. Online, however, our sense of self remains largely invisible to us [2]. As individuals scroll on algorithmic feeds, online platforms monitor and assemble a mosaic of our digital footprints (e.g. browsing histories, reactions, mouse movements, and clicks) scattered across multiple sites. Collected data are used to analyze or predict aspects of an individual's life, including work performance, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behavior, and location [11].

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To ensure humans’ right to understand and contest AI-driven decisions, HCI and Explainable AI (XAI) scholars have prioritized algorithmic transparency. Traditional algorithm visualizations often overwhelm end-users with complexity [7], while proprietary algorithms remain protected by trade secrets [8]. Recent personalized XAI approaches aim to make explanations more accessible and relevant to users’ individual contexts, moving beyond one-size-fits-all solutions [4]. Systems like CHAITok and The Algorithm have attempted to simulate recommendation patterns using small user-selected datasets [1, 12], but these simulations lack the authenticity of users’ actual digital footprints.

Meanwhile, Large Language Models (LLMs) offer promising capabilities for XAI [14]. For example, some work has investigated using LLMs to directly explain ML models [3, 9], to understand user questions to generate the appropriate explanation [13] or to transform explanations into natural language narratives [15]. We believe that LLMs can be used to generate plausible inferences from a user’s digital footprint, potentially bridging the gap between complex algorithmic systems and intuitive user understanding.

In this study, we provide users with a personalized data visualization that we call “Algorithmic Mirror” for real-world algorithmic investigations. Algorithmic Mirror acts as a digital mirror, bringing together fragmented digital footprints from online platforms and time periods to reveal how platforms and algorithms shape users’ inner lives over time. Our key design concepts are:

- (1) *Interactive Map Visualization*: reassembling scattered digital footprint into a single map of personal digital footprint and inferences;
- (2) *Hypothetical Inference*: simulating how algorithms might interpret user digital footprint and infer personal characteristics generated by Large Language Models (LLMs) without access to the actual proprietary algorithms used by social media platforms;
- (3) *Temporal Dimension*: utilizing long-term data to enable users to reflect on the effects of recommendation algorithms and their actions over time.

We then examine how this design can support users’ reflection on their online behavior and data, with the following research question:

RQ: How might a tool for simulating algorithmic inference be used to facilitate critical reflection over data?

Taken together, our findings contribute to the research on XAI for enhancing users’ critical algorithmic literacy, as well as the ability to understand and evaluate how algorithms work and impact information we see and decisions we make.

2 DESIGN PROTOTYPE: ALGORITHMIC MIRROR

Drawing on previous personalized XAI tools, we propose Algorithmic Mirror. This design prototype aims to bring together scattered digital footprints into a single map and visualize how algorithms interpret users’ footprints. By doing so, it highlights the influence of filtering algorithms on content exploration and algorithmically-mediated lives.

Algorithmic Mirror is built upon a publicly-available language model-powered knowledge exploration system called Latent Lab [6]. The tool provides an automated and easy-to-use pipeline for converting high-dimensional unstructured data into interactive 2D map visualizations. The interface allows users to explore labeled clusters of similar topics and search by semantic context. In our study, participants obtained their YouTube watch history via Google Takeout and uploaded the data to Latent Lab. Below, we discuss the four main key design components of Algorithmic Mirror.

Interactive Map Visualization Algorithmic Mirror leverages Latent Lab to create an interactive 2D map of video data, where each dot represents a video. Transcripts are embedded via OpenAI’s text-embedding-ada-002 model and then reduced to two dimensions using UMAP. Clusters signify semantic similarity, and overlaid contour lines illustrate data density. Users can pan, zoom, and view high-level or detailed labels and contours, supported by an occlusion

Fig. 2. Algorithmic Mirror Interface. We highlight four main components of the interface with dashed lines. The watched videos are in pink, searched terms in purple, watched videos after searching in yellow, watched advertisements in green, and watched shorts videos in blue.

algorithm that prioritizes popular topics for legible labeling. Clicking any point opens a sidebar showing the detailed view with the video’s header image, title (with a direct link), and its full transcript.

Topic Extraction and Data Processing Algorithmic Mirror uses Latent Lab to model how recommendation systems analyze digital footprints, inferring user interests and preferences. Latent Lab automatically extracts up to three primary topics from each video transcript using GPT-4o. These topics are aggregated, ranked, and embedded to position them within semantically relevant areas of the map, forming a hierarchical topic tree that scales from broad to specific themes as users zoom. This structure ensures users can navigate clusters with increasing detail and thematic nuance.

Summarization and Timeline The summarization bar samples transcripts visible on the map, summarizes them via GPT-4o, and presents a concise overview of the current map region. A timeline slider lets users filter videos by date, dynamically updating contour lines and labels to highlight how content shifts over time.

Dataset Overlay Latent Lab allows users to overlay one dataset onto another, enabling the exploration of one dataset in the context of another by projecting the overlaid points into the semantic space defined by the target dataset’s UMAP reducer. This process is non-commutative, meaning overlaying dataset A onto dataset B yields different results than overlaying B onto A, as the spatial relationships depend on the target dataset. In Algorithmic Mirror, this feature is used to analyze cross-platform content, such as overlaying YouTube viewing data onto Spotify listening history (or vice versa) to reveal semantic relationships. (see Figure 4 for visualization of dataset overlay).

Fig. 3. Temporal evolution of Algorithmic Mirror. We animate participant’s watch history month by month, starting from September 2018. The first visualization shows data until Jan 2021, the second until Jan 2023, and the third until Jul 2024.

3 USER STUDY

Participants We recruited participants through convenience and snowball sampling methods, screening 25 initial respondents to select 14 eligible participants who were 18 or older, visited YouTube daily, and typically browsed from the YouTube homepage. Despite efforts to achieve demographic diversity, our final participant pool showed balanced gender representation but was skewed toward higher education levels, with all participants holding bachelor’s degrees, potentially indicating above-average technical and data literacy compared to the general population.

Study Procedure During a 60-minute user study, each participant was asked to interact with Algorithmic Mirror and answer questions. Each user study contained two parts (see Table 2 for details of interview questions). Firstly, in a walk-through and think-aloud of Algorithmic Mirror, participants were allowed to interact freely with Algorithmic Mirror and asked to think aloud, providing insight into their thought processes as they tested the tool [5]. Secondly, participants provided feedback on specific design functionalities and were encouraged to critique and reimagine Algorithmic Mirror. All the interviews were conducted in Microsoft Teams due to geographical constraints. The study was approved by the university’s ethics committee.

4 RESULTS

We discuss how Algorithmic Mirror can be used to facilitate critical reflection over platform practices on data collection and data inference.

Users developed meta-cognitive awareness of their online behavior After each user uploaded their watched YouTube history (20,000 to 40,000 videos), these records were transformed into topics they could explore. We observed increased engagement after participants started zooming specific interests, eventually clicking on individual dots to look at the details of specific videos. This personalized experience helped the majority of participants ($n = 10/14$) recall content they had watched, including content they did not remember (P5: “I have gone down like nail, like fingernail polish rabbit hole.”). This process of recalling and reviewing their content consumption patterns triggered surprise at the breadth and volume of their content consumption across categories (P1: “It’s scary to realize that I’m watching things without awareness.” P2: “I’m surprisingly unaware of the gap between my perception and my actual self.”).

Algorithmic Mirror allows data from multiple platforms to be combined into a single visualization. Three participants imported Spotify listening history alongside YouTube viewing data. Comparing maps between YouTube-only, Spotify-only, or a combined integrated visualization, P2 realized how “different personalities exist within each platform.” (see Figure 4 for visualization of cross-platform visualization).

Users recognized how their interests have evolved over time Most participants ($n = 12/14$) interacted with the timeline slider to observe the evolution of their interests over time, often triggering what P5 termed ‘nostalgia’.

Participants ($n = 8/14$) often first clicked the ‘Play’ button which animates the map month by month, noting that this process allowed them to see what P5 termed “*watching myself grow*”. P2 stated, “*The tool allows me to think more deeply about the temporal depth and maturity of my interests*,” observing changes in YouTube usage from initially using it as a music tool to later relying more on recommendations. P4 echoed this insight: “*I like the fact that I can see it over time... it does reflect interests that I’ve had as a person*.” P5 described how “*it takes me back to what I was doing or who I was in the past*.” In multiple instances, participants then selected specific time ranges by choosing a start and end date in the Timeline Slider. P6 asked: “*What was I looking up when I was taking these exams and when I was on this holiday?*” and used the timeline slider to examine those two moments.

Users critically examined inferred data Most participants ($n = 9/14$) found that the categories and summaries inferred by Algorithmic Mirror were accurate representations of their interests. They expressed fascination and discomfort with seeing a simulation of how recommendation algorithms on online platforms might interpret their behavior. Looking at the generated summary, P13 noted, “*The summary looks right. It’s always interesting when something interprets you to back yourself*”. This curiosity often led the participants to examine the implications of these algorithmic inferences critically, with P10 noting that the inferred ‘weight loss’ category was for ‘fitness content’ (“*I think watching fitness content means that you can get a lot of ads that have to do with weight loss*”). Participants also reflected on the broader effect that platform profiling had on their content consumption. P4 wondered, “*Has this mirror changed because I changed it or has it changed because the algorithm or some other external thing has changed it?*”

Users critically examined collected data Looking at maps of inferred interests and generative summaries, some participants ($n = 5/14$) questioned why Algorithmic Mirror was so accurate. They experimented with the Timeline Slider to see how much and how long their history had been recorded by YouTube (3 years on average, up to 10 years). P5 observed, “*They [recommendation algorithms] remember you, like how you were interested*.” P12 questioned if collecting such data allows platforms to shape future interests, noting, “*how would it [recommender system] try to track my interest over time and project new interests? [...] I can imagine it can try to predict how my personality would evolve*.”

Users reflected on alignment between consumption and interests Watching their maps evolve over time, a majority of participants ($n = 12/14$) noted that Algorithmic Mirror helped them reflect on whether the viewing consumption aligned with their personal goals and interests. P6 found the tool helpful in identifying content that “*doesn’t necessarily spark joy*” but they still continue to watch, prompting them to question engagement with such content. P9 noted, “*The proportion of hobbies I want to pursue [...] isn’t that high*.” P11 expressed shock, “*I was surprised to see how much time I spent watching things I didn’t really want to watch*.”

Our findings suggest that algorithmic inference simulations from personal digital footprint enable users to critically evaluate how data collection and inference practices shape their personalized content experiences.

5 CONCLUSION

Our research explored how Algorithmic Mirror could facilitate users’ critical reflection over their data on online platforms. Our research offers insights into how individuals can recognize and identify themselves in the digital age to promote more conscious engagement with online content. Our findings suggest design recommendations in XAI field to reassemble scattered digital footprints into a single map, simulate algorithmic inference with LLMs, as well as display a timeline for capturing evolving patterns. We emphasize engaging, user-centric presentations of online behaviors and inferred preferences can enhance critical algorithmic literacy. Future work should aim to reach broader populations with varying educational backgrounds and literacy levels, should promote features that encourage independent reflection, and should follow participants’ interactions over a longer period.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aila ElKattan and Lujain Ibrahim. 2024. The Algorithm. <https://www.whatsthealgorithm.com/about>.
- [2] David Beer. 2019. *The Data Gaze: Capitalism, Power and Perception*.
- [3] Amrita Bhattacharjee, Raha Moraffah, Joshua Garland, and Huan Liu. 2024. Towards LLM-guided Causal Explainability for Black-box Text Classifiers. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.13340> arXiv:2309.13340 [cs]
- [4] Cristina Conati. 2024. Personalized Human-Centered Explainable AI. (2024).
- [5] Lynne Cooke. 2010. Assessing Concurrent Think-Aloud Protocol as a Usability Test Method: A Technical Communication Approach. *IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication* 53, 3 (Sept. 2010), 202–215. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPC.2010.2052859>
- [6] Kevin F Dunnell. 2023. Latent Lab: Exploration Beyond Search and Synthesis. (2023).
- [7] Chen He, Denis Parra, and Katrien Verbert. 2016. Interactive Recommender Systems: A Survey of the State of the Art and Future Research Challenges and Opportunities. *Expert Systems with Applications* 56 (Sept. 2016), 9–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2016.02.013>
- [8] Rob Kitchin. 2017. Thinking Critically about and Researching Algorithms. *Information, Communication & Society* 20, 1 (Jan. 2017), 14–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2016.1154087>
- [9] Nicholas Kroeger, Dan Ley, Satyapriya Krishna, Chirag Agarwal, and Himabindu Lakkaraju. 2024. In-Context Explainers: Harnessing LLMs for Explaining Black Box Models. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.05797> arXiv:2310.05797 [cs]
- [10] Jacques Lacan. 1977. *The Four Fundamental Concepts of Psycho-analysis*. Hogarth Press.
- [11] Frank Pasquale. 2015. *The Black Box Society: The Secret Algorithms That Control Money and Information*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge.
- [12] Ge Wang, Jun Zhao, Samantha-Kaye Johnston, Zhilin Zhang, Max Van Kleek, and Nigel Shadbolt. 2024. CHAITok: A Proof-of-Concept System Supporting Children’s Sense of Data Autonomy on Social Media. In *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, Honolulu HI USA, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642294>
- [13] Elizabeth Anne Watkins, Emanuel Moss, Ramesh Manuvinakurike, Meng Shi, Richard Beckwith, and Giuseppe Raffa. 2024. ACE, Action and Control via Explanations: A Proposal for LLMs to Provide Human-Centered Explainability for Multimodal AI Assistants. (2024).
- [14] Xuansheng Wu, Haiyan Zhao, Yaochen Zhu, Yucheng Shi, Fan Yang, Tianming Liu, Xiaoming Zhai, Wenlin Yao, Jundong Li, Mengnan Du, and Ninghao Liu. 2024. Usable XAI: 10 Strategies Towards Exploiting Explainability in the LLM Era. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.08946> arXiv:2403.08946 [cs]
- [15] Alexandra Zytek, Sara Pidò, and Kalyan Veeramachaneni. 2024. LLMs for XAI: Future Directions for Explaining Explanations. (2024).

A PARTICIPANT DEMOGRAPHICS

ID	Gender	Age Range	Origin	Education	Daily YouTube Session Length
1	Female	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< an hour
2	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< two hours
3	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	> two hours
4	Female	18-25	Indian	Master	< an hour
5	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< an hour
6	Female	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< an hour
7	Female	18-25	Chinese	Bachelor	< two hours
8	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< two hours
9	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< an hour
10	Male	25-30	American	Master	> two hours
11	Female	25-30	American	Master	< two hours
12	Female	18-25	American	Master	< an hour
13	Male	18-25	Indian	Master	< an hour
14	Male	25-30	Japanese	Master	> two hours

Table 1. Participant Demographics. The sample shows an equal gender distribution (7 males, 7 females), with participants predominantly in the 18-25 age range (11 participants). Most participants are of Japanese origin (8), followed by American (3), Indian (2), and Chinese (1). All participants hold higher education degrees (8 Bachelor’s, 6 Master’s). YouTube viewing habits indicate most participants (11) watch less than two hours daily, with only 3 participants watching more than two hours.

B INTERVIEW PROTOCOL

Interview Protocol: Interaction with Algorithmic Mirror
<p>Phase 1: Initial Exploration Please browse this interface freely (10 minutes)</p> <p>Phase 2: User Experience Assessment</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What aspects of the tool did you find particularly effective or appealing? 2. What features or elements did you find challenging or less useful? 3. Could you suggest specific improvements that would enhance your experience with the tool? <p>Phase 3: Future Usage Intent Would you be interested in continuing to use this interface after the study concludes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ If yes: What would motivate your continued use? ◦ If no: What factors influence your decision not to continue? <p>Phase 4: Reflection Process Evaluation What are your overall thoughts on this reflection process?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ How effective was it in promoting self-reflection? ◦ What impact did it have on your understanding of your online behavior?

Table 2. Semi-structured Interview Protocol

C DATASET OVERLAY (SPOTIFY AND YOUTUBE)

Fig. 4. Left panel: Algorithmic Mirror of Spotify listening history, Right panel: Multi-platform Algorithmic Mirror overlaying YouTube viewing data onto Spotify listening history (or vice versa) to reveal semantic relationships. Users can toggle between single-dataset views or combined overlays, with distinct colors (e.g., green for YouTube and purple for Spotify) highlighting cross-platform patterns and thematic connections.